

**C1 Power system development & economics
PS3: Planning the cyber-physical system**

Data-driven distribution network expansion planning for hosting new green investments

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SUMMARY

As distribution networks transition to active systems, Distribution System Operators (DSOs) require advanced planning tools to delay or avoid costly infrastructure investments by procuring operational flexibility from controllable loads or generators. This paper proposes a modular framework for multi-year distribution network planning, developed and enhanced within the context of the SYNERGIES, OPENTUNITY, and ODEON Horizon Europe projects. The methodology integrates an efficient Mixed-Integer Linear Programming (MILP) optimization engine with high-performance computing modules, including a Fixed-Point Iteration (FPI) power flow engine, pre-trained AI analytics for forecasting, and Dynamic Time Warping (DTW) for scenario clustering. To address the limitations of traditional planning algorithms, which are based on limited network observability and lack of controllable devices, this framework is integrated with proper Energy Data Space (EDS) implementations that guarantee large and secure data exchanges between DSOs, Transmission System Operators (TSOs) and Aggregators. EDSs also provide AI tools to process and refine these data. Moreover, the modular design of the proposed planning framework can incorporate LLM-based forecasting and distribution network reconfiguration, as feasible but promising extensions. Results from diverse pilot sites in Greece, Spain, and Slovenia demonstrate that the suggested methodology achieves significant cost reductions, successfully defers expensive grid upgrades through strategic flexibility procurement, and maximizes Renewable Energy Sources (RES) hosting capacity. Simulations confirm that a flexibility rate of 10%-20% can effectively mitigate network stress and reduce total expenditures compared to traditional worst-case planning approaches.

KEYWORDS

Distribution Network Planning, Energy Data Spaces, Digital Twins, AI-analytics, Data-driven decision making

Introduction

The urgent need for energy system decarbonization and the transition toward a cleaner and more resilient electricity grid require a fundamental shift in the way distribution networks are planned. In this evolving context, Distribution System Operators (DSOs) must explicitly account for the increasing penetration of controllable distributed energy resources (DERs), including photovoltaic systems, wind generation, storage units, electric vehicles, and flexible demand. Traditional, reinforcement-driven planning approaches are no longer sufficient to address the resulting operational complexity and uncertainty. Instead, DSOs must transition from passive infrastructure expansion toward active planning frameworks that systematically exploit the controllability of DER assets, complemented by flexibility services available in market-based environments.

Distribution network planning is further challenged by uncertain load evolution, the variability of renewable generation, and the need to optimize both capital (CAPEX) and operational expenditures (OPEX). To address these challenges, this paper introduces advanced planning tools that enable DSOs to co-optimize conventional grid reinforcements (e.g., line and substation upgrades) with the utilisation of DER controllability and the procurement of flexibility through local or wholesale flexibility markets.

The efficacy of these planning tools is highly dependent on the seamless integration of data provided by DSOs and other stakeholders (Aggregators, Local Energy Communities, TSO) through a common Energy Data Space (EDS). Energy Data Spaces act as secure, federated repositories that enable standardized data exchange while ensuring interoperability, sovereignty and transparency. Within the EDS, AI-analytics toolboxes are provided, which leverage EDS data to generate high-accuracy demand and generation forecasts. By employing advanced models - such as Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) neural networks, ARIMA for time-series decomposition, and kernel-based regression - the system produces long-term demand and generation evolution scenarios that serve as input for planning algorithms.

Furthermore, this work addresses the inherent limitations of traditional long-term forecasting, which often relies solely on historical numerical data. We propose an innovative forecasting methodology that integrates Large Language Models (LLMs) to parse unstructured public information—such as policy announcements and infrastructure reports—into structured indicators for demand evolution. This allows DSOs to anticipate emerging demand drivers that historical data alone might overlook.

The backbone of the suggested planning algorithms is called a Digital Twin (DT) of the distribution network, which facilitates the simulation of long-term DN operations. The DT processes raw DSO data and AI-generated forecasts to execute state-of-the-art optimization algorithms, allowing DSOs to interactively assess various RES and EV penetration scenarios. Unlike conventional "worst-case scenario" planning, this multi-year optimization approach minimizes the combined costs of reinforcements and flexibility acquisition.

Additionally, while classical planning assumes a fixed radial topology, this paper explores Distribution Network Reconfiguration (DNR) as a strategic planning lever. By incorporating topology optimization into the multi-year formulation, the model prioritizes Non-Wire Alternatives (NWA), ensuring that physical reinforcements are only triggered once the operational reconfiguration envelope is exhausted.

The research and tools presented in this work are derived from the outcomes of three Horizon Europe projects: SYNERGIES [1], OPENTUNITY [2] and ODEON [3]. These initiatives focus

on the integration of Energy Data Spaces with an ecosystem of AI-analytics and Smart Energy Applications. The proposed planning framework has been rigorously tested across diverse demonstration sites in Greece, Spain, and Slovenia. Key findings demonstrate significant cost reductions for network operators, a marked delay in expensive infrastructure upgrades due to efficient flexibility procurement, and a measurable reduction in network losses and load shedding.

Multi-year optimal planning for active distribution networks

The rapid growth of distributed energy resources, electrification of demand, and increased variability in power flows challenge traditional distribution network planning approaches that rely primarily on deterministic peak-load criteria and grid reinforcement solutions. Recent regulatory developments, and in particular the new ACER decision on flexibility needs assessment [4], introduce a harmonized European framework that requires DSOs to systematically identify, quantify, and consider flexibility as a viable alternative to conventional grid investments.

Mathematical optimization frameworks, particularly Mixed-Integer Linear Programming (MILP), are now widely employed to balance between traditional infrastructure investments and the operational costs of flexibility services, thereby facilitating cost-effective grid expansion [5-7]. Contemporary research focuses not only on increasing operational efficiency but also on harmonizing capital investments in physical assets with deployments of smart technologies. This dual approach ensures that modern distribution systems remain resilient and sustainable despite the uncertainties of future demand and generation.

To account for the stochastic nature of renewable energy, many planning models for Active Distribution Networks (ADNs) utilize scenario-based and stochastic optimization techniques. These methodologies simulate a broad spectrum of potential future states, allowing planners to optimize network expansion and operation under high-variability conditions [7], [9]. Additionally, multistage planning approaches enable DSOs to make incremental decisions, revisiting and adjusting expansion plans as new data or technologies emerge, which significantly mitigates the financial risks of long-term planning under uncertainty [10]. Finally, bi-level optimization models have gained attention; these frameworks separate strategic investment decisions (upper level) from daily operational tasks such as load balancing, network reconfiguration, and storage scheduling (lower level), ensuring that long-term strategies remain operationally feasible [6].

The objectives in network expansion planning typically revolve around the optimization of reliability and cost-efficiency. In accordance to currently applied DSO practices that emphasize on the minimization of Total Expenditure, the simultaneous minimization of CAPEX and OPEX has become a standard objective. These expenditures include the economic costs and benefits provided by flexibility services, like demand response and energy storage [6], [11]. Moreover, many optimization models integrate key reliability indices, such as Expected Energy Not Served (EENS) and the System Average Interruption Duration Index (SAIDI), ensuring that cost-minimization does not compromise power quality [6].

This work assesses a novel distribution network planning methodology that integrates flexibility as a planning variable alongside traditional network assets, reflecting the logic introduced by the ACER framework. The proposed methodology introduces a two-layer planning process. First, flexibility needs are estimated through scenario-based power flow and security analyses that capture congestion, voltage violations, and contingency conditions under future demand and generation trajectories. For each identified network constraint violation, the

required upward and downward flexibility volumes are quantified in terms of capacity, activation duration, temporal availability, and probability of activation. Second, flexibility and grid reinforcement options are jointly evaluated within a techno-economic planning framework, enabling DSOs to compare long-term investments against flexibility procurement under regulatory and operational constraints. The methodology supports transparent decision-making, regulatory compliance, and efficient use of flexibility resources, providing a practical pathway for embedding flexibility-aware planning into future DSO development plans.

First Implementation of a multi-year investment planning application - the SYNERGIES project

Energy Application Framework for Distribution Network Planning

The core contribution of this work lies in the deployment of the network planning tool as a modular "Energy-as-a-Service" (EaaS) solution. Unlike conventional monolithic planning software, this architecture allows DSOs to acquire the tool as an independent service or as a functional component within a broader Energy Data Space (EDS) ecosystem. This flexibility enables DSOs to execute the application on private cloud infrastructure using localized datasets or within a federated EDS environment, where data can be seamlessly exchanged with other energy value chain actors, such as TSOs, Flexibility Service Providers (FSPs) and prosumers.

The proposed solution integrates a sophisticated computational engine - called a Digital Twin of the network in the context of SYNERGIES project - with a user-centric energy application designed for scenario management and results visualization.

Long-Term Asset Sizing Engine

The computational core of the application processes both primary grid data provided by the DSO and demand and generation forecasts generated by pre-trained AI models. Using the network topology datasets and the forecasts, the engine utilizes advanced mathematical programming to evaluate long-term evolution pathways and determine optimal investment strategies.

Investment Planning and Prioritization Interface

The energy application provides an environment where DSO end-users can model various scenarios and interact with the planning engine to derive actionable investment insights. The interface is divided into two primary functional modules:

- **Future Scenario Design Manager:** This module offers an interactive platform for DSOs to define annual growth rates for demand and generation over a 5-to-10-year horizon. Users can simulate the integration of specific assets - such as RES, EVs, and Battery Energy Storage Systems (BESS) - by specifying their capacity and geographic placement within the network. These custom scenarios are then transmitted to the computational engine (Digital Twin) to evaluate technical feasibility and infrastructure requirements.
- **Planning Results Visualization Engine:** Once the optimization is complete, this component translates complex algorithmic outputs into an intuitive dashboard. It

presents detailed technical specifications for suggested reinforcements, provides a financial and technical assessment of new asset installations, and offers comparative analytics to help DSOs prioritize different evolution scenarios based on cost-efficiency and grid reliability.

Mathematical Problem Formulation of optimal multi-year investment planning

The multi-year optimization problem is defined by the following objective function, which aims to minimize the net present value of total expenditures:

$$\min f = \sum_{y=1}^T (R_y - D_y^{LR}) IC_y^{LR} + R_y (C_y^{flex} + C_y^{loss}) \quad (1)$$

In this formulation, $R_y = \prod_{t=1}^y \frac{1+Inf_t}{1+Int_t}$ represents the net present value coefficient, while $D_y^{LR} = R_T \frac{EL_{LR}(T-y)}{EL_{LR}}$ accounts for the equipment's depreciation at the end of the planning horizon T (where EL_{LR} denotes the expected lifespan of a line).

The primary cost components include the CAPEX for line reinforcement (IC_y^{LR}) and the OPEX, which consists of flexibility procurement costs $C_y^{flex} = C_y^{PG} + C_y^{QG} + C_y^L$ (active & reactive power control from DERs and active power flexibility from loads) and the economic impact of power losses (C_y^{loss}).

To maintain computational tractability while capturing system stress, we define a set of characteristic days \mathcal{D} . This set includes four critical scenarios: annual maximum and minimum load, and annual maximum and minimum generation. Flexibility pricing is integrated as input time-series data derived from market forecasts.

Operational Constraints

Power flow dynamics within the distribution network have been considered, using the DistFlow equations. To ensure convexity, the power balance per line is treated with a SOCP relaxation. This relaxation is considered exact in this context, as power loss minimization is included in the objective function. We also enforce standard operational constraints for nodal voltage limits, lines thermal capacity and transformer overloading limits. The operational margins (capacity) for generation and demand flexibility have been defined also as constraints.

The line parameters (resistance and impedance) are determined by the installed line type (see Table 1: Technical data & total (installed) costs for conductor alternatives [12], [13]) and on the upgrade decision variables. Bilinear terms in the power flow equations, stemming from the product of decision-dependent impedance and squared currents, are handled through standard big-M linearization techniques. Moreover, the optimization algorithm incorporates constraints and cost models for transformer and substation upgrades, following the same mathematical logic as the line reinforcement formulation.

SYNERGIES pilot outcomes

The efficacy of the proposed planning framework is validated using a localized medium-voltage (MV) distribution system in the Greek demo site of SYNERGIES project. This test network is a 130-bus, 20 kV system comprising 129 branches, 13 load buses, 4 PV generator buses, and a single substation. Users can define a planning horizon of either 5 or 10 years within the

application. Operating constraints specify voltage limits at $\pm 10\%$ of the nominal value. Economic parameters include a 1-4% interest rate and a 2% inflation rate. Based on recent market trends in Greece, the costs for upward and downward flexibility are set at 400 euros/MWh and 300 euros/MWh, respectively, while active and reactive power losses are valued at 20 euros/MWh. Table 1 details the technical specifications and costs for the available conductor types. The tool was built using the Python-based Pyomo library and solved using the Gurobi optimizer.

Table 1: Technical data & total (installed) costs for conductor alternatives [12], [13]

Available Conductors				
Type	R (Ω/km)	X (Ω/km)	I (kA)	Cost (euros)
25/4 ACSR	1.274	0.417	0.115	10000
35/6 ACSR	1.268	0.422	0.16	20000
50/8 ACSR	0.576	0.397	0.224	30000
70/12 ACSR	0.404	0.386	0.295	36000

Future Scenario Design

This study evaluates two distinct pathways for renewable integration: a "light" (S1) and a "heavy" (S2) RES penetration scenario. In scenario S1, three PV systems are added to buses 44, 62, and 76 in years 4, 6, and 8. Conversely, scenario S2 involves eight PV units installed across buses 44, 60, 62, 70, 76, 80, 90, and 120 between years 4 and 8. A 10% flexibility rate—defined as the ratio of available flexibility to nominal power—is assumed for all assets in both cases. The cumulative capacity reaches 1.24 MW for S1 and 3.24 MW for S2. Crucially, the spatial and temporal placement of these assets is determined by the end-user via the application’s interface (Fig. 1) rather than the optimization algorithm itself.

Figure 1: SYNERGIES - User interface for interactive scenario configuration.

Visualization of Planning Outcomes

The application provides the DSO with a clear timeline of required interventions and their associated costs for each scenario (Fig. 2). These actions include either the activation of upward/downward flexibility or the implementation of physical line upgrades. In the S1 (light RES) scenario, the model suggests two line reinforcements in the second year, totaling 8270.23 euros. In contrast, the S2 (heavy RES) scenario yields a significantly lower total cost of 1486.98

euros, requiring no line upgrades and utilizing 3.05 MW of flexibility. This suggests that higher levels of controllable RES can significantly improve ADN operational efficiency.

Figure 2: SYNERGIES - Optimization outputs: Yearly flexibility requirements.

Case Studies

Two specific investigations demonstrate the tool’s usefulness for investment planning. First, we analyzed the impact of varying flexibility rates for the two PV scenarios (S1 and S2). As shown in Fig. 3, a critical threshold exists for each scenario (10% and 8% respectively); beyond these points, the DSO can effectively substitute expensive infrastructure investments with flexibility procurement. This allows DSOs to establish precise flexibility procurement targets [4] and design prosumer incentives.

Figure 3: SYNERGIES - Sensitivity analysis of the two PV penetration scenarios under varying flexibility rates.

Second, the tool was used to assess the network’s RES hosting capacity, a vital metric for modern decarbonization strategies [14]. Fig. 4 indicates that the tested ADN possesses substantial potential for RES integration. Interestingly, because the new assets are considered flexible, the typical "U-curve" associated with grid stress [15] is not observed even at high penetration levels. This is due to the DSO’s ability to procure downward flexibility from PVs during peak production hours, thereby justifying further RES investments in this specific network.

Figure 4: SYNERGIES - Evaluation of scenario S2 with constant 10% flexibility and varying installed RES capacity.

Methodological Enhancements - the OPENTUNITY project

Based on the planning framework implemented in the context of the SYNERGIES project, computational and methodological enhancements were performed within the OPENTUNITY project, to address its efficient application on large historical datasets of high-resolution demand and generation measurements. Specifically, the tool has been augmented with advanced modules designed to handle high-resolution timeseries without sacrificing accuracy. These enhancements include the implementation of a high-performance Fixed-Point Iteration power flow engine for accelerated system analysis and a Dynamic Time Warping based scenario clustering technique, which ensures that representative operating conditions are captured with higher structural fidelity than traditional Euclidean methods.

Power Flow Module

Power flow simulations are essential for validating planning results and identifying representative operating scenarios, but high-resolution, multi-year analyses are computationally prohibitive with conventional solvers. Since distribution networks are typically operated radially—an assumption commonly adopted in planning as a conservative worst-case—this structural property can be exploited to significantly reduce computational complexity. Leveraging recent advances in multicore CPUs and GPUs, the proposed approach adopts a fixed-point iteration (FPI) power flow algorithm tailored to radial distribution systems, introduced in [16], offering high numerical stability, guaranteed convergence under suitable conditions, and excellent scalability. The method is based on successive approximation of nodal voltages using nominal complex power injections and is highly amenable to parallel implementation.

In practice, the approach enables ultra-fast large-scale simulations: for a representative feeder in the Spanish demo, ten years of hourly power flow scenarios (87,600 cases) were solved in approximately one second—over two orders of magnitude faster than Newton–Raphson implementations using standard tools—demonstrating its suitability for computationally intensive distribution planning studies.

Scenario Clustering

DSOs typically possess historical datasets spanning multiple years, containing detailed time-series information on demand and distributed generation. While such extensive datasets provide valuable insight into system behavior, their direct use in distribution network planning

algorithms is generally not computationally efficient. Consequently, it is necessary to extract a reduced set of representative daily scenarios that adequately capture the main characteristics and variability of the original data while maintaining tractability for planning studies.

The annual time series is reshaped into 365 daily load profiles, each represented by a 24-hour net load curve. The resulting set of 365 daily profiles is then clustered into three distinct representative groups on days. The clustering process is performed using time series clustering techniques [17]. Time series clustering employs Dynamic Time Warping to quantify the similarity between daily load profiles. DTW is a distance measure specifically designed for time series data, allowing for non-linear alignments along the temporal axis. In contrast to Euclidean distance, which enforces a strict point-to-point comparison between values at identical time instants, DTW enables the alignment of similar patterns that may occur at slightly different times.

In this work, DTW is formulated as shown in (10), with the associated constraints defined in (2)-(4), for two time series consisting of 24 samples corresponding to hourly daily power curves.

$$DTW(x, y) = \min_{\pi} \sqrt{\sum_{(i,j) \in \pi} d(x_i, y_j)^2} \quad (2)$$

where $\pi = [\pi_0, \dots, \pi_K]$ is a path that satisfies the following properties:

- It is a list of pair of indexes i, j with $0 \leq i, j \leq 23$

$$\pi_0 = (0,0) \quad \& \quad \pi_K = (23,23) \quad (3)$$

- For all $k \geq 0$, $\pi_k = (i_k, j_k)$ is related to $\pi_{k-1} = (i_{k-1}, j_{k-1})$ as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} i_{k-1} &\leq i_k \leq i_{k-1} + 1 \\ j_{k-1} &\leq j_k \leq j_{k-1} + 1 \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

For each cluster, the daily profile with the highest peak net power is chosen as the representative scenario, ensuring that critical operating conditions are captured.

Finally, relying exclusively on the worst-case scenario may result in an overestimation of both the flexibility requirements for an entire cluster of days—since not all days necessarily exhibit operating conditions that require flexibility to resolve constraint violations and the associated network power losses. To mitigate this effect, two correction factors are introduced: one accounting for power losses and one reflecting flexibility utilization. These factors are subsequently passed to the optimization module and incorporated as weighting terms in the objective function.

OPENTUNITY pilot outcomes

The advanced Network Planning Tool developed in the OPENTUNITY project is being applied in the project's pilot sites, examining various use cases in different EU countries, including Spain, Slovenia and Greece.

The power flow results are presented in a user-friendly way, with information on lines and buses for the examined planning period in map-based visualizations, as depicted in Fig. 6.

Figure 5: OPENTUNITY - Map Visualization engine

The tool highlights how strategic use of larger flexibility resources, if available, can defer costly investments (Fig. 10). In this case, the flexibility for both RES and demand is increased to 20%. It is evident that the optimization algorithm can effectively utilize the offered flexibility to avoid costly upgrades in the grid.

Figure 6: OPENTUNITY - Investment deferral for the Spanish demo site

The network planning tool also offers the option for RES capacity maximization (Fig. 11), ensuring that RES capacity expansion is closely aligned with existing grid constraints. In this case, the tool identifies optimal locations of new RES power plants, while considering the budget constraints defined by the distribution system operator.

The screenshot shows a web-based interface for parameterizing an optimization scenario. At the top, the 'Optimization Goal' is set to 'Optimal Investment for RES Maximization'. Below this, the 'Economic Parameters' section includes three input fields: 'Interest Rate (%)' with a value of 5,00, 'Flexibility Price (€/MWh)' with a value of 50,00, and 'Budget Constraint (€)' with a value of 40000,00. The 'Flexibility Parameters' section includes two input fields: 'Maximum Flexibility (% of available power)' with a value of 5,00 and 'RES Power Factor Limit' with a value of 0,80. Below these sections are three dropdown menus: 'Optimization Results', 'Power Flow', and 'Save System Planning'. A 'Calculate' button is located to the right of the 'Power Flow' dropdown.

Figure 7: OPENTUNITY - Optimization scenario parameterization for hosting capacity maximization

Further Extensions - the ODEON project

While the core planning framework and optimization engine have reached a high level of maturity through development in the SYNERGIES and OPENTUNITY projects, the increasing requirements for modern distribution grids in the era of decarbonization and electrification necessitate further innovation. To this end, the ODEON project focuses on expanding the current toolset including state-of-the-art additional features. By integrating advanced LLMs for context-aware demand forecasting and incorporating Distribution Network Reconfiguration as a strategic planning lever, these future extensions aim to further reduce investment risks and maximize the utilization of existing grid assets.

Long-term load forecasts

The first extension is to develop, implement and validate an innovative long-term load forecasting methodology for distribution networks by integrating LLMs with conventional load forecasting techniques. The task addresses the limitations of traditional long-term forecasting approaches, which primarily rely on historical consumption data and a limited set of numerical socio-economic indicators, by systematically incorporating unstructured public information that reflects emerging demand drivers.

The task will be structured in three main activities. First, a comprehensive data gathering and screening activity will be carried out, focusing on publicly available sources relevant to electricity demand evolution, including national statistical reports, government gazettes, policy announcements, and local news or social media content. Data quality checks and relevance filtering will be applied to ensure the robustness of the collected information. Second, an LLM-based indicator extraction pipeline will be developed, enabling the automated parsing of unstructured textual data and the identification of qualitative socio-economic signals (e.g., infrastructure investments, housing development, electrification trends). These signals will be translated into structured, quantitative indicators suitable for modeling purposes. Third, the extracted indicators will be integrated into a long-term load forecasting model, combining historical demand data with LLM-derived features through regression or machine-learning techniques, allowing the model to capture both historical trends and forward-looking contextual drivers.

The task will be validated through a real-world case study at distribution level, using data from a selected Greek prefecture. The performance of the proposed LLM-enhanced forecasting approach will be benchmarked against conventional historical-data-driven models, assessing improvements in forecast accuracy and interpretability. The outcome of this task will be a scalable and replicable methodology that enables DSOs to better anticipate medium- to long-term demand evolution, supporting more informed grid planning and investment decisions under conditions of high uncertainty.

The Perspective of Network Reconfiguration in Expansion Planning

Long-term distribution system expansion planning traditionally assumes a fixed radial topology, addressing voltage and thermal violations exclusively through physical reinforcements, such as new feeders, conductor upgrades, or transformer capacity expansion. This classical approach often leads to higher capital expenditures and underutilized infrastructure. As we have highlighted in the Introduction [1](#), the paradigm shift toward ADNs allows for effective distributed flexibility procurement and DNR during real-time operation, which can be used as a strategic planning lever. Integrated planning that coordinates topology changes with reinforcement can significantly defer high-CAPEX investments and optimize asset utilization over multi-year horizons [5], [18].

In the formulation of the optimal multi-year planning as a mathematical optimization problem, DNR expands the feasible solution space. On the one hand, the topology can be optimized to redistribute power flows, relieve line congestions, and maintain nodal voltages between the accepted limits. On the other hand, DNR allows for load transfer between adjacent substations, delaying transformer upgrades. In both cases, DNR can lead to the satisfaction of operational constraints avoiding costly reinforcements.

Conclusion

This work presented a comprehensive energy application framework for the multi-year optimal planning of ADNs. By leveraging the interoperability of Energy Data Spaces, the developed tool enables DSOs to transition from static planning to a dynamic, data-driven paradigm.

The implementation and testing of the tool across multiple European demo sites in the context of SYNERGIES and OPENTUNITY projects establish a robust baseline for grid optimization. Further enhancements, that are being performed in the ODEON project, include the integration of LLMs to refine long-term load forecasting and the incorporation of automated network reconfiguration to further expand the DSO's operational envelope.

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